

Studies on the sorption of cadmium(II) on the synthetic gel potassium fluorophlogopite

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Sorption of Cd has been studied on the synthesized gel close to potassium fluorophlogopite [KMg₃(Si₃AlO₁₀)F₂] as a function of initial solution concentration at pHs 2, 4 and 7. The parameters like equilibration time, weight of the exchanger and temperature have also been investigated. The uptake of Cd has been expressed in terms of distribution coefficient (K_d).

Contamination of the environment by heavy metal ions in the industrial area near Gwalior, Malanpur and Ghirongi has led to the health risks of human being and animals^{1,2}. The majority of these pollutants are waste products of industrial and metallurgical processes. The effluents from electroplating plants in particular have high concentrations of dissolved metals.

Cadmium is an extremely toxic metal commonly found in industrial work-places. The most common methods of removal of metals are chemical precipitation, solvent extraction, dialysis, electrolysis, electrolytic extraction, cementation, reverse osmosis, evaporative methods, biosorption etc². The development of synthetic inorganic materials with higher selectivity of ions received much attention during the last two decades³. Out of a variety of materials reported the mica group of minerals have not yet been fully investigated in this regard.

Here we report the results of sorption of Cd^{II} on one of the mica group of minerals potassium fluorophlogopite gel KMg₃(Si₃AlO₁₀)F₂.

Results and Discussion

The chemical composition of the synthesized material was checked by EDAX analysis which confirms the metals K, Mg and Al to be present in the ratio 1 : 4 : 2 by weight. Thus, its composition is very close to the fluorine-mica KMg₃(Si₃AlO₁₀)F₂. The X-ray powder diffraction pattern of the sample shows the maxima at 36.68 counts/s, *d*-spacing 1.53347 Å, relative intensity (%) 100.00, angle $\theta_2 = 60.30612$, background (counts/s) = 86.66 and significance 1.03, suggesting that the gel shows a separation of two hexagonals by a distance of 1.53347 Å. Thus, the hydrothermal phase resembles disordered potassium fluorophlo-

pite phase which may gradually be ordered to 1M type. The ordering of phase begins at 425° below which the mineral exists in a gel-like phase. There are hexagonal vacant sites available for the exchange of ions⁴.

The values of K_d versus time reveal that the extent of sorption for Cd^{II} increases and the state of equilibrium is reached after 8 h. Hence, for further studies time of equilibration was taken as 8 h. The data of Table 1 suggest that on increasing exchanger-to-aqueous phase ratio, the K_d values increases due to the availability of more number of sites for exchange. The thermodynamic studies for sorption of Cd^{II} show decrease in free energy of the system with increase in temperature and which suggests that selectivity of Cd^{II} increases with temperature. Finally, it is concluded that the sorption studies of Cd^{II} on this synthetic ion exchanger has a great potential at pH 4 and also the exchanger has high affinity for Cd^{II} at higher temperature.

Table 1. Weight variation of potassium fluorophlogopite mmols Cd^{II}/50 ml = 0.364, weight of exchanger = 100 mg
Temp. = 25°, pH of solution = 4.0, equilibration time = 8 h

Weight of exchanger g	Initial [Cd ^{II}] mmols of Cd ^{II} in 50 ml	Cd ^{II} in solid phase Total mmols	Cd ^{II} remaining in solution after equilibration mmols/50 ml	K_d
0.03	0.364	0.163	0.201	356.5
0.06	0.364	0.177	0.187	472.6
0.09	0.364	0.216	0.148	726.1
0.10	0.364	0.255	0.109	1166.7
0.12	0.364	0.264	0.0997	1324.8
0.15	0.364	0.277	0.0874	1582.9

Experimental

The hydrothermal gel having chemical composition close to that of fluorine-mica mineral potassium fluorophlo-

logopite $\text{KMg}_3(\text{Si}_3\text{AlO}_{10})\text{F}_2$ was synthesized by hydrothermal method in a teflon-lined stainless steel pressure vessel at 200° for 72 h. Its chemical composition was checked for metal K, Mg, Al and Si using EDS test. The XRD pattern of the gel was recorded on a computer interfaced PW 3011 (mini prop.) diffractometer system and the EDS pattern recorded (EDAXZAF quantification) at SICART, Vallabh Vidyanagar.

A weighed amount of this gel was equilibrated with required concentrations of Cd^{II} ions at pHs 2, 4 and 7. The exchanger was also equilibrated with Cd^{II} solution in a thermostated water-bath at 25, 35 and 45° . The selectivity of Cd^{II} ions by this gel is expressed in terms of distribution coefficient values, which is defined as

$$K_d = \left[\frac{C_o}{C_e} - 1 \right] \frac{V}{M}$$

where, C_o and C_e are respectively initial and equilibrium concentrations of Cd^{II} , V is the volume of solution (ml) and M the mass of gel(g).

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